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Benedicamus Domino tropes in the monastery of Benedictine nuns at St George's, Prague

ONE of the most distinctive features of the music repertoire in Bohemia is the prolonged and active cultivation of certain musical genres, such as tropes to the Mass Proper and Mass Ordinary, simple polyphony or polytextual motets.¹ The presence of a large number of tropes for *Benedicamus Domino* chants documented in late medieval sources from Bohemia from the late 13th to the early 16th centuries is in accordance with this general picture. The prominent position of *Benedicamus* tropes in the late medieval repertoire is often interpreted as an expression of increased interest in regular strophic forms in Bohemia, which, at the latest by the second half of the 14th century, led to the establishment of a strong tradition of *cantiones*—strophic songs with and without refrains, in Latin and vernacular, some of which were soon also incorporated to the Roman liturgy in Prague.² The importance of *Benedicamus* tropes for the constitution of vernacular songs was first acknowledged by Guido Maria Dreves, who referred specifically to the Czech and German traditions. The section that he labelled 'Rufe' (Exclamations) in his edition of some 30 *Benedicamus* tropes was included in the first volume of the *Analecta hymnica* series.³ Since then, the number of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes documented in Bohemian manuscripts has been substantially enlarged and so too the variety of traditions that cultivated this genre in their liturgy: the Prague diocesan liturgy, the Utraquist liturgies and sources from monastic traditions.⁴

The corpus of tropes that survives in manuscripts from St George's convent at Prague Castle stands out as a particularly important collection.⁵ The nunnery, situated in close proximity to St Vitus's Cathedral,

was established in 976 by the ruling dynasty of knights and later kings from the Přemyslid family, shortly after the constitution of the Prague bishopric (973). Until the outbreak of the Hussite wars (1419), it served as the prime institution for noble women in the country and was closely associated with the politics and prestige of the Přemyslid dynasty.⁶ The nuns were typically recruited from the leading noble houses and a female descendent of the ruling dynasty often stood at the head of the convent.⁷ Throughout the Middle Ages, the convent remained a relatively small community. According to the confirmation books, only 39 nuns participated in the election of the abbess in 1401; the confirmation document of 1386 mentions no more than 18 nuns, including the resigning abbess Catherine (*domicella Katherina*).⁸ In the last decade of the 13th century, a scriptorium was established at the monastery, as well as a collegium of canons who conducted the liturgy together with the nuns and were in charge of pastoral care. Although the convent practised the Benedictine liturgy and was influenced by the Hirsau reform, it also adapted much music from Prague, and accommodated many chants associated—in some cases exclusively—with the liturgical practice of the adjacent St Vitus's Cathedral.⁹

This period is closely associated with the work of two noble women: the abbess and Přemyslid princess, Abbess Kunhuta (Kunigundis) (1265–1321), daughter of King Přemysl Otokar II (1233–78) and sister of King Wenceslas II (1271–1305); and Žofie (Sophia), who served as the abbess until 1302 and again after Kunhuta's death in 1321. Kunhuta received the office at the personal intervention of her brother, King Wenceslas II, after she

returned to Prague following her divorce from the Mazovian prince Boleslav II (1253/58–1313) (see [illus.1](#)). Entering a monastery was not a new experience for her, but rather a return to a milieu that she knew intimately. Raised in the royal nunnery of the order of St Claire Na Františku in Prague, established by her aunt, St Agnes of Bohemia, she left it only at the request of her brother in order to contract a politically strategic marriage to the Mazovian prince. A rich documentation and variety of new music thus emerged at a time when St George's monastery was subjected to new impulses from outside, be it from the highly cultivated milieu of the Prague royal court, or from other, mainly mendicant, orders.¹⁰

No fewer than nine manuscripts from the monastery—mostly compiled at the end of the 13th and the first decades of the 14th centuries, when the rich music and liturgical tradition there reached its peak—contain 42 *Benedicamus Domino* tropes.¹¹ Numerous manuscripts, among them processional and the so-called *corpora officiorum* from this

period, demonstrate particularly strong interest in late poetic liturgical forms.¹² Apart from the *Benedicamus Domino* chants with and without tropes, they include some dozen individual readings of the *Visitatio sepulchri* play and a selection of characteristic late medieval liturgical poetry, such as rhymed Offices (*historiae*) or sequences, many of them recently composed in Bohemia, perhaps even in the monastery's close vicinity.¹³ A vivid liturgical and devotional practice is further documented by collections of devotional and mystical texts that were complemented by book illuminations of the highest quality.¹⁴

Although this repertory has been available in a modern edition for more than three decades, it is still surrounded by many unanswered questions. We are confronted here with an unusually rich and strongly connected repertory, suddenly emerging and exclusively witnessed in manuscripts dated around 1300 from the heart of Central Europe. The manuscript picture—confined to the late 13th and early 14th centuries—does not allow us to follow the development of this repertory over a longer period of time or to define individual stages of reception, modification and individual local enlargements. [Table 1](#) orders the chants according to their frequency of occurrence in manuscripts from St George's, with an indication of their position in the manuscript (the number in round brackets). A list of the manuscripts designated by the letters A–K in the table and the main text can be found in the Appendix.

Statistically, this repertory has a clear focus on Christmastide (with eleven chants), Marian liturgy (eight chants) and the feast of the Church Dedication/feast of St George (five chants). It may seem surprising that only two *Benedicamus Domino* tropes are documented for Easter, one of them (*Surrexit Christus hodie*, no.39) appearing in a single inscription among additions in the 14th-century psalter (H). This evidence, however, only confirms the popularity of the main trope for the Feast of Resurrection, *Benedicamus Exultemus et letemur* (no.1) in the monastery. It is the only chant that appears in all of the collections of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes and in some cases also in a specific liturgical context, as a part of Sunday processions during Eastertide (see below). Notably, no chant is

1 Passionale of the Abbess Kunhuta, National Library of the Czech Republic, Ms. xiv A 17, fol.1r (published with the permission of the National Library of the Czech Republic)

Table 1 Tropes to the *Benedicamus Domino* in manuscripts from St George's monastery, Prague

No.	Incipit	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	K	Feast	Mel.
1	Exultemus et letemur	× (1)	× (12)	× (9)	× (20)	× (7)	× (10)	× (1)	× (7)	× (1)		Resurrectio Domini	
2	Puer natus in Bethleem	× (7)	× (2)	× (1)	× (16)	× (2, 14)	× (1)	× (2)	× (2)			Nativitas Domini	
3	Nos respectu gratie ⁺	× (12)	× (6)	× (3)	× (3)	× (6)	× (5)	× (7)	× (4) [#]			Epiphania Domini	
4	Patrem parit filia	× (13)	× (7)	× (2)	× (1)	× (3)	× (2)	× (3)				Nativitas Domini	
5	Quem laudant angeli	× (17)	× (10)	× (12)	× (21)	× (12)	× (8)	× (12)				--	
6	Nos factura Dei	× (18)	× (11)	× (13)	× (23)	× (13)	× (9)	× (13)				--	
7	Iohannes flos ecclesie	× (27)	× (16)	× (14)	× (4)	× (8)	× (12)	× (8)				De s. Iohanne Baptista	
8	Festivali melodia	× (30)	× (20)	× (18)	× (12)	× (10)	× (15)	× (10)				De BMV	
9	Benedicamus flori orto	× (33)	× (26)	× (22)	× (22)	× (1)	× (11)	× (15)				De BMV	
10	Iohannes postquam senuit	× (10)	× (4)	× (6)	× (17)	× (4)	× (3)	× (4)				De s. Iohanne Evangelista	↓↑
11	Petrus clausus ergastulo	× (28)	× (18)	× (16)	× (5)	× (9)	× (13)	× (9)				De s. Petro	= 10 ↓↑
12	Paradisi prepositus Michael	× (5)	× (25)	× (24)	× (8)	× (11)	× (11)	× (11)				De s. Michael	= 10 ↓↑
13	In laudibus infancium	× (11)	× (5)	× (8)	× (9, 19)	× (4)	× (4)	× (6)				De ss. Innocentibus	= 10 ↓↑
14	Sanctifica pater pie	× (26)	× (27)	× (25)	× (18)	× (15)	× (14)	× (14)				--	
15	Benedicamus devotis laudibus	× (8)	× (3)	× (4)	× (10)	× (16)	× (6)	× (6)	× (3) [*]			De s. Stephano	
16	Benedicamus Marie virginis	× (35)	× (5)	× (5)	× (14)	× (17)	× (7)	× (14)				De BMV	= 15
17	Martir dei Wenceslaus	× (4)	× (24)	× (23)	× (7)	× (7)						De s. Wenceslao	= 10 ↓↑
18	Splendor patris et sol	× (29)	× (17)	× (15, 26)	× (11)	× (11)						Nativitas Domini	
19	Verum sine spina	× (32)	× (23)	× (21)	× (6)	× (6)						De BMV	
20	Amor patris et filii	× (3)	× (32)	× (10)	× (10)	× (10)						De sancto Spiritu	
21	Ad honorem sempiterni regis	× (16)	× (15)	× (11)								De sancto Spiritu	
22	Hoc in festo meste mesto	× (21)	× (22)	× (20)								Dedicatio Ecclesiae	

Table 1 Continued

No.	Incipit	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	K	Feast	Mel.
23	Nostra mater ecclesia	× (24)	× (19)	× (17)								Dedicatio Ecclesiae = 10 ↓↑	
24	Stirps yesse flourerat	× (31)	× (21)	× (19)								De BMV	
25	Procedentem sponsum ⁺	× (6)	× (1)		× (2)				× (1)			Nativitas Domini	↓↑
26	Hoc in templo sonet melos	× (2)	× (14)									Dedicatio Ecclesiae; Georgii Nativitas Domini	
27	Hec est dies salutaris	× (14)	× (8)									De BMV	
28	Virga Yesse flourit	× (15)	× (9)									--	
29	Beata nobis hodie	× (19)	× (29)									--	
30	Laus Domino resonet	× (20)	× (30)									Nativitas Domini	
31	Regi psallens hec concio	× (22)	× (28)									--	
32	Redemptori altissimo	× (25)	× (31)									--	
33	Benedicamus Domino hodie	× (36)	× (13)									Resurrectio Domini	
34	Huius in natalicio	× (9)			× (15)							Nativitas Domini = 10 ↓↑	
35	Benedicamus in laude Ihesu ... matri	× (34)							× (5)		×	Purificatio BMV = 9	
36	Inixum scale	× (23)									(2)	Dedicatio Ecclesiae	= 10 ↓↑
37	In hoc festo sanctissimo			× (7)	× (13)	× (5)		× (5)				--	
38	Zacheus Ihesum suscipit								× (8)			Dedicatio Ecclesiae	↓↑
39	Surrexit Christus hodie								× (6)			Resurrectio Domini	
40	Benedicamus regi apostolorum										×	De ss. Petri et Pauli	
41	Benedicamus precursoris regi										(3)	De s. Iohannis Baptista	

Table 1 Continued

No.	Incipit	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	K	Feast	Mel.
42	Benedicamus in laude Ihesu... suum	36	32	25	22**	16***	15	15	8	1	4	Corpus Christi	= 9
	Total number of tropes												

Key: **A** = CZ-Pu VII G 16; **B** = CZ-Pu VI G 10a; **C** = CZ-Pu XII E 15a; **D** = CZ-Pu VII H 1; **F** = CZ-Pu VI G 5; **G** = CZ-Pu XIII H 3c; **H** = CZ-Pu XVI A 18; **I** = CZ-Pu VI G 3b; **K** = CZ-Pu XIII E 14b

↑ = *Stimmtausch* melody

* *Splendor patris* (no.18): 2x; ** *In laudibus infancium* (no.13): 2x; *Puer natus in Bethlehem* (no.2): 2x

fragmentary inscription (manuscript **H**);

+ two-part inscription in at least one manuscript

prescribed specifically for the feast of St Ludmila, the grandmother of St Wenceslas and, with him, co-patron of Bohemia, despite her being buried in St George's church and venerated with special emphasis in the monastery.

Out of 42 chants, 16 can be designated a 'core' repertory regularly found in six or more manuscripts from the late 13th century onwards (nos.1–16). Processionals **A** and **B** clearly contain the most extensive sets of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes, and **B** is one of the oldest manuscripts in this source group, dated by Plocek to c.1300.¹⁵ Eight tropes (nos.26–33) occur only in these two largest processional collections, while outside **A** and **B**, nine (nos.17–25) are found in only one or two other manuscripts. The remaining chants were recorded in various manuscripts, and two of them survived in only a single inscription (nos.38 and 39).

Benedicamus In hoc festo sanctissimo to St Wenceslas (no.37), a contrafact of *Iohannes postquam senuit* (no.10), presents a special case. It is missing in both manuscripts **A** and **B**, but occurs frequently as an addition to the 'core' repertory in other *Benedicamus Domino* collections. Four *Benedicamus Domino* tropes (nos.40–2) were added as late as in the 17th century into a beautifully illuminated 12th-century psalter. These four tropes stand out as rare evidence of a prolonged practice of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes in the early modern period.¹⁶

As to the selection of tropes in individual manuscripts, the whole corpus is strikingly unsettled: not only in the choice of different chants, but also in their order. It seems, therefore, that there was no carefully organized compilation in the monastery library that served as a definitive model or exemplar for individual copies. Rather, each collection reflects an individual pragmatic decision on the part of its scribe and it is possible in only a few cases to understand the strategy at work, such as collating chants in groups according to their liturgical destination—as in manuscript **C**, with small groups of tropes for Christmastide or Pentecost—or according to their melodic families, as in manuscript **G** (*Iohannes postquam senuit*, *In hoc festo sanctissimo* and *In laudibus infancium*, Table 1, nos.10, 37 and 13).

Ex.1 The trope *Iohannes postquam senuit* for the feast of John the Baptist from B, fol.117v

Io - han - nes post - quam se - nu - it, As John grew older,

Chri - stus e - i ap - pa - ru - it. Christ appeared to him.

The collection is remarkably diverse as to the provenance of the different *Benedicamus Domino* tropes. On the one hand, there are pieces that were widely known in Central European territory: *Benedicamus Flori orto*,¹⁷ *Iohannes postquam senuit*¹⁸ or the two-part *Procedentem sponsum*.¹⁹ On the other, a number of tropes had their origins west of the river Rhine, and appear in the collection of St George's monastery in Prague isolated from the main area of their distribution: *Regi psallens hec concio* (no.31),²⁰ *Laus Domino resonet* (no.30),²¹ *Splendor patris et sol* (no.18) or *Ad honorem sempiterni regis* (no.21).²² A repertory of such mixed composition and with striking connections to the west is nothing unusual in the Prague context. A similar situation pertains in the repertory of Mass Ordinary tropes in the neighbouring St Vitus's Cathedral. There, however, it was thanks to a rather unusual one-off act: the purchase in 1234 of a 12th-century manuscript of foreign origin containing a collection of Mass Ordinary tropes, the so-called St Vitus's troper, which fundamentally influenced the constitution of the cathedral's repertory and its characteristic profile in the 13th and the 14th centuries.²³ Is it possible that we are dealing here with a similar, and very particular, mode of repertory dissemination? As will be shown later in more detail, there are direct connections between the *Benedicamus Domino* and Mass Ordinary trope repertories; it is possible that some *Benedicamus* tropes arrived in Prague, and from the west, through similar channels before they were also assimilated into the repertory of St George's.

Looking closer at the 'core repertory' of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes (nos.1–16 in Table 1), we can observe a balance between chants that were probably received from surrounding, and in some cases distant, regions, and those that were—judging from the current source evidence—known either in close proximity to, or directly at, St George's. Most

of the tropes follow a regular strophic form, but there are a few that are technically *prosulae*, textings of pre-existing melodies (Table 1, nos.9, 15 and 16). Moreover, in this group there are chants with melodic types or specific melodies that enjoyed some popularity in the convent and were adapted to new texts. The trope *Iohannes postquam senuit* for the feast of John the Baptist (Table 1, no.10) is perhaps the best example (see ex.1). Its characteristic *Stimmtausch* melody had been widely distributed since the 11th century and is found in manuscripts from Central Europe from the 12th century onward.²⁴ A closely similar *Stimmtausch* melody can be detected in three other chants from the 'core repertory', all of them intended for important feasts of the church year, which were also celebrated in the monastery: *Petrus clausus ergastulo* for St Peter (Table 1, no.11), *Paradisi prepositus* for St Michael (Table 1, no.12) and *In laudibus infancium* for the feast of the Holy Innocents (Table 1, no.13). The desire to furnish the repertory for major festivities during the church year with proper chants, for which certain melodic types could be used, is manifested by four other tropes which also adopt this same melody appearing in St George's collections: *Nostra mater ecclesia* for the feast of the Church Dedication (Table 1, no.23), *Huius in natalicio* for Christmas (Table 1, no.3), *Martir Dei Wenceslaus* for St Wenceslas (Table 1, no.17) and *In hoc festo sanctissimo* (Table 1, no.37), which could be used for various feasts throughout the church year. When speculating about the origin of some of these tropes, the chant for Wenceslas at least is a strong candidate for domestic composition, given his status as the main patron of Bohemia. Important in this context, however, is the testimony of such a strong group of contrafacts, documented around 1300: it seems that the first tropes with this melody, among them *Iohannes postquam senuit*, must have been known in the

Ex.2 The trope *Exultemus et letemur* from C, fol.195r

1. E - xul - te - mus et le - te - mur ho - di - e, Let us rejoice and be joyful today

di - es i - sta di - es est le - ti - ci - e. this day is the day of joy.

Al - le - lu - ia, re - sur - re - xit do - mi - nus, Alleluia, the Lord has risen.

- | | | |
|----|---|--|
| 2. | Exultandi et letandi tempus est,
pascha nostrum Christus immolatus est.
Alleluia, resurrexit dominus. | It is time for rejoicing and joy
Christ our Passover has been sacrificed.
<i>Alleluia, the Lord has risen.</i> |
| 3. | Ad sepulchrum mulieres veniunt,
et ab angelo responsum accipiunt.
Alleluia, resurrexit dominus. | The women come to the grave
and they receive an answer from the angel.
<i>Alleluia, the Lord has risen.</i> |
| 4. | Ille nitor indicavit gaudium
Quia vivit vera vita hominum.
Alleluia, resurrexit dominus. | He, the splendour [i.e. the angel], announced the joy
That the true life lives.
<i>Alleluia, the Lord has risen.</i> |
| 5. | Ergo nostra sit devota concio,
Resurgenti benedicat domino.
Alleluia, resurrexit dominus. | Therefore let our assembly be devout
[Let us] bless the risen Lord.
<i>Alleluia, the Lord has risen.</i> |

monastery for some time, becoming a popular part of the nuns' repertory before they became models for new contrafacts.²⁵ *Stimmtausch*-type melodies were evidently popular with St George's nuns, and can be identified not only in other *Benedicamus Domino* tropes (*Procedentem sponsum*, Table 1, no.25, or *Zacheus Ihesum suscipit*, no.38), but also in the repertory of hymns. The hymn *Lux vera lucis radium* to St Ludmila, based on a *Stimmtausch* melody, is recorded in a contemporary collection of Offices (*corpus officiorum*) in its two-part arrangement.²⁶ Unfortunately only the last section of the trope *Nos respectu gratie* (Table 1, no.3), with a two-part arrangement of its refrain (*Audi, audi, audi nos*), survives in the psalter from the mid 14th century (manuscript H). But its partial survival nevertheless confirms the use of simple polyphony at St George's. Compared to the advanced culture of polyphonic singing in other nunneries outside Bohemia, however, this represents a relatively

modest, even archaic, mode of performance. And it seems that tropes documented elsewhere in polyphonic arrangements survived—and were most probably performed—in St George's monastery in monophonic versions, such as *Benedicamus devotis laudibus* (Table 1, no.4), *Regi psallens hec concio* (no.33), *Ad honorem sempiterni regis* (no.23) or *Laus Domino resonet* (no.32), discussed in detail below.

As the following examples demonstrate, the collection of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes from St George's monastery is in many ways extremely heterogeneous. The trope *Exultemus et letemur*, for the feast of the Resurrection (ex.2), deserves attention for several reasons. It is omnipresent in medieval sources of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes from St George's, in some cases appearing outside the trope series, in the context of processional chants for Easter (manuscripts A, B, G and I). The trope originated in the west, where it is documented from 1100 to the 15th century

in southern and northern France, as well as on the Iberian Peninsula; St George's convent cultivated its performance in a shortened and slightly modified form.²⁷ The subject of the trope—the celebration of Christ's Resurrection and the Visit of three Marys at Christ's sepulchre in the third and fourth stanzas—was likely responsible for its popularity in the convent (see *ex.2*).²⁸ The text gives a dense and detailed account of the crucial scene of the Resurrection feast, exactly the scene that was spectacularly performed as part of the *Visitatio sepulchri* play by female convent members and male canons during the Easter Vigil. This scene at the tomb and the short dialogue between the three Marys and the angel is also the central theme of a second Easter trope, *Surrexit Christus hodie* (no.39), documented in a single inscription from the mid 14th century.²⁹

Exultemus et letemur is extremely joyful, as indicated by its open exclamation, which is reiterated (in a modified form) in the second stanza. The tone of joy and praise is further confirmed by the short 'Alleluia' refrain, here amplified by including the reason for that joy: 'Resurrexit Dominus' (the Lord has risen). The text is written economically, employing short but characteristic phrases, some of them borrowed from other chants, as, for example, the Easter Alleluia *Pascha nostrum Christus immolatus est* in the second stanza,³⁰ or *Dies est leticie*, a phrase appearing in many liturgical chants with the incipit *Adest dies leticie* or *Ecce dies leticie* in the opening stanza.³¹ The melody of the trope has a similarly effective economy: both lines of the stanza and the refrain make use of a similar melodic arc in the first half (*g-c'*, *d-g-c'*, respectively), moving the second halves either to the lower *d* (the first line), or through *d* to the final *e* (the second line and the refrain). The use of smooth embellishments, where western manuscripts have syllabic movement, is striking.³²

A rubric (*In vesperis benedicamus*) in the processional (I) from the beginning of the 14th century specifies that *Exultemus et letemur* was performed during Vespers. This is confirmed by the entry in the *Liber ordinarius* from the mid 14th century, where this trope is prescribed as the last piece for Vespers on the first Sunday after Easter:

Ad vespervas super psalmos antiphona *Alleluia* ut antiphona *Vespere autem sa(bbati)*. Psalmus *Confiteantur*,

quod *Alleluia* ab hic usque in Penthecosten omnibus dominicarum prioribus cantantur vesperis. Capitulum *Omne quod natum est*. Responsorium *Dum transisset sabbatum*. Imnus *Ad cenam agni*. Versiculus *Gavisi sunt discipuli*. In evangelio antiphona *Cum esset sero die*, oratio *Concede quesumus omnipotens deus*. *Benedicamus Exultemus* a quatuor dominabus cantetur.³³

For Vespers the antiphon for all psalms *Alleluia*, as [i.e. with the same melody as the antiphon] *Vespere autem sa(bbati)*. Psalm *Confiteantur*, and this *Alleluia* is sung from now until the feast of Pentecost on Sundays during first Vespers. Chapter *Omne quod natum est*. Responsoy *Dum transisset sabbatum*. Hymn *Ad cenam agni*. Versiculus *Gavisi sunt discipuli*. Antiphon to Magnificat *Cum esset sero die*, collect *Concede quesumus omnipotens deus*. *Benedicamus Exultemus* is sung by four women.

The instruction given in the *Liber ordinarius*, namely that the trope should be performed by four nuns only ('a quatuor dominabus cantetur'), is intriguing. The character of the trope itself seems to invite the participation of the whole convent in performance, specifically joining in the singing of the recurring refrain 'Alleluia'. It appears, however, that *Exultemus et letemur* was considered a chant for only select female soloists at St George's. According to the *Liber ordinarius*, the same number of nuns (*cantrices*) took responsibility for performing solo portions of chants during the liturgy.³⁴

The presence of a refrain—short or more elaborate—constitutes an important characteristic of the whole repertory at St George's. Plocek specifically considered *Exultemus et letemur* to be the oldest example of this characteristic feature documented in sources from Bohemia.³⁵ A refrain could be formulated as a short exclamation (typically 'Alleluia' or its simple extension), but could also embody a principal ideal that would be emphasized in its repetition. The following pair of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes, *Iohannes flos ecclesie* for John the Baptist (*Table 1*, no.7) and *Festivali melodia* for the Virgin Mary (*Table 1*, no.8), effectively illuminates both strategies (*exx.3a* and *3b*).

Both tropes belong to the 'core repertory' of St George's monastery and are only rarely documented elsewhere.³⁶ Both use similar melodic material, formulated as a sequence of ascending and descending phrases through the full ambitus of the D (Dorian) authentic mode, which are strongly reminiscent of the strategy of *Stimmtausch* melodies found

Ex.3a The trope *Iohannes flos ecclesie* in B, fol.165r

Io - han - nes, flos ec - cle - si - e,
 Bap - tis - ta re - gis glo - ri - e,
 na - tus est no - bis ho - di - e.
 Gau - de - a - mus!

Ex.3b The trope *Festivali melodia* in D, fol.166r

1. Fes - ti - va - li me - lo - di - a *With festive melody*
 te lau - da - mus, o Ma - ri - a, *We praise Thee, O Mary*
 quam com - men - dat pro - phe - ci - a, *as prophecy recommends.*
 ma - tris pri - vi - le - gi - o. *Privileged mother,*
 Chorus
 Re - gem re - gum pe - pe - ri - sti *you gave birth to the King of Kings*
 mi - ro pu - er - pe - ri - o. *by miraculous childbirth*

2. O Maria, mater dei,
 te rogamus tamquam rei,
 effectum da nostre spei.
 Matris privilegio
 regem regum peperisti
 miro puerperio.

O Mary, Mother of God
 we ask you to
 give effect to our hope.
Privileged mother,
you gave birth to the King of Kings
by miraculous childbirth

elsewhere in the St George's collection.³⁷ The only exception (and a desirable contrast) can be found in the middle phrase, which is descending with unexpected leaps, and which—as modern performance has shown—presents a challenge even for relatively experienced singers. Overall, however, the basic melodic outline is quite simple and can be often reduced to a basic phrase that appears elsewhere in the late medieval chant repertory (for example, the opening phrase is essentially a simple melodic curve *d-a-b-a-g-f-e-d*). Yet the music has a pronounced smooth and elegant character, thanks to short embellishments of prevailing 3rd to 6th tones employed in course of the whole piece. Each stanza of the trope *Iohannes flos ecclesie* is concluded by a short joyful exclamation *Gaudeamus!*, a conclusion also found in other medieval chants.

The Marian trope *Festivali melodia* makes use of similar musical material, but introduces a refrain of a different, more extensive, character. The refrain is three full lines and so equal in length to the trope stanzas (see [ex.3b](#)). As a result, the whole chant seems to operate on two levels: the four stanzas of text are formulated as a graceful prayer to the Virgin Mary, which can be read and understood independently of the refrain. The recurring three-line refrain is not, in its content, part of the prayer. Although it is also addressed to the Virgin, it praises her role as the mother of God, and the King of Kings (*regem regum*), with the melody for this latter text abandoning its smooth ornamental character to become more dynamic, employing a popular melodic formula in the upper register (*a-c'-d'-a*), which is associated primarily with the Easter sequence *Victime paschali laudes* (stanzas *Agnus redemit oves / Mors et vita duello*).

The two next examples return to the remarkable connection of several tropes preserved at St George's with the western tradition of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes. The *Benedicamus* trope *Exultemus et letemur* already demonstrates that the repertory's reception and its further cultivation in Prague was accompanied by modifications, such as a shortening of the number of stanzas, changes in the text and a preference for smooth, embellished melodies. *Benedicamus Splendor patris et sol* ([Table 1](#), no.18) presents another such case: not only does it also demonstrate that tropes were

modified at St George's, but it reveals a so far overlooked relationship between the corpus of tropes to the *Benedicamus Domino* at St George's and the repertory of tropes to the Mass Ordinary preserved in the adjacent St Vitus's Cathedral. The oldest and, so far, the only known copy of *Splendor patris* outside St George's is in the troper E-Mn 289, dated c.1140.³⁸ Once again, the text preserved in St George's nunnery is shorter: it consists of one stanza of four lines and a *Benedicamus* acclamation rather than of two stanzas of six lines with two corresponding acclamations *Benedicamus / Deo gracias* recorded in E-Mn 289 (see [Table 2](#), cols.a and b).

The melody of *Splendor patris* transmitted at St George's can best be characterized as an embellished version of the melodic contour captured in E-Mn 289, with one major modification. While the six-line stanza of E-Mn 289 consists of three melodically identical double-lines, the trope in St George's monastery, reduced to four lines, introduces new material in the third line, based on a contrasting movement towards the upper finalis *d'*. In such a modified form, the melody of *Splendor patris* in St George's is almost identical with the melody of the trope *Sanctus Deus pater, iudex iusticie*, documented in the St Vitus's troper from the end of the 12th century ([Table 2](#), col.c).³⁹ The direct relationship between the two tropes in the Prague sources is also visible in the text, employing similar phrases in the first and the third lines (highlighted in bold in [Table 2](#)). A small change in text at the end of the second line of *Splendor patris* at St George's, which refers to the text of *Deus pater, iudex*—with *materie* in E-Mn 289 becoming *miserie* in the two Prague sources—indicates that both tropes were transmitted for some time together and/or cultivated in the same milieu.

The surprising connection between the *Benedicamus* and *Sanctus* tropes in Prague, along with evidence of their interaction during transmission, opens up a whole series of questions that go beyond the scope of this article, relating, for example, to the much-discussed question of the origin of St Vitus's troper.⁴⁰ Questions surrounding the source of the trope, its reception and the mode of its cultivation in St George's are more relevant to the repertory and practices of singing in the convent. The influence of the adjacent

Table 2 The trope *Benedicamus Splendor patris et sol* and related tropes

a	b	c
E-Mn 289	St George's monastery	St Vitus's troper (CZ-Ph Cim 4)
c.1140 <i>Benedicamus Splendor patris</i> (Capella Palatina, Palermo)	c.1300 <i>Benedicamus Splendor patris</i> (St George's, Prague)	1180–1200 <i>Sanctus Deus pater iudex</i> (origin unknown; in Prague since 1234) Sanctus Deus pater , iudex iusticie , nos illustra celitus hodie. Deus homo, sed sine carie, nos de lacu educ miserie .
Splendor patris et sol iusticie fit particeps nostre materie. Intrat ventrem, sed sine semine, egreditur de matre virgine. Hic ingressus et hec egressio Deitatis fiunt probacio. Ergo benedicamus domino. Caro deus et factor omnium (etc.)	Splendor patris et sol iusticie fit particeps nostre miserie . Intrans ventrem, sed sine semine, egreditur ex matre virgine. Ergo benedicamus domino.	
The glory of the father and the sun of justice Will be part of our being. He entered the womb, but without seed And came out of a virgin mother. This coming and his departure (going) Will be a proof of divinity. Then let us give thanks to the Lord.	The glory of the father and the sun of justice Will be part of our misery. He entered the womb, but without seed And came out of a virgin mother. Then let us give thanks to the Lord.	God, the Father, the judge of justice, Enlighten us today from above. God, the Man, but without sin, Lead us out of the lake of misery.

St Vitus's Cathedral (from which no copy of the trope *Splendor patris* itself survives) seems the most plausible explanation, and it is also possible that four copies of *Splendor patris* in St George's manuscripts from c.1300 reflect the most recent integration of this trope into the convent's repertory. It cannot be ruled out, however, that *Splendor patris* was incorporated into the liturgical repertory in St George's much earlier, perhaps even by the first half of the 13th century, when Prague experienced an influx of poetic genres, specifically pieces with a much earlier transmission in the west.⁴¹ *Benedicamus Exultemus et letemur*, another trope with its roots in the west, was already a firm part of the liturgical repertory at St George's by the end of the 13th century and must therefore have been in use in the convent for a longer period of time than in the western context in which it was originally conceived.

The last *Benedicamus Domino* trope to be discussed here in detail is of an entirely different

character: *Laus Domino resonet* (Table 1, no.30) for Christmas (ex.4).

This trope is an excellent example of the after-life of the Ars Antiqua repertory in the late Middle Ages. The text and melody of *Laus Domino resonet* is known from manuscript *W*₂, where it accompanies the motetus voice of a three-part monotextual motet on the plainchant tenor EIUS, the concluding phrase of the responsory *Stirps Yesse* from the feast of the Nativity of the Virgin Mary.⁴² In Gordon Athol Anderson's transcription, the motet moves in the regular pattern of the third mode, supported by a similarly regular pulse of perfect harmonies between upper voice and tenor. Such striking regularity inspired Anderson to observe that '[t]he mood of the motet is one of calm serenity and matches the contemplative nature of the text, the joy and praise arising from the heart and inner spirit of the worshipper, not in shouts of acclamation'.⁴³ Nothing of that remains in the monophonic version of this trope preserved in St George's sources. The motetus voice,

Ex.4 The trope *Laus Domino resonet* in A, fols.182v–183r

Laus Do - mi - no re - so - net om - ni - um iu - bi - lo.
 Qui con - do - lens ho - mi - ni per - di - to na - tus ex Ma - ri - e vir - gi - nis u - te - ro.
 O mi - ra res dig - na pre - co - ni - o
 Sol ru - ti - lans o - ri - tur de su - o sy - de - re ful - gi - do.
 Hunc i - gi - tur psal - lat hec con - ci - o cum pi - o a - ni - mo
 Do - mi - no.

now a monophonic trope, can only with difficulty be designated ‘melodious’, in terms of late medieval chant practice in Central Europe. Compared to the majority of the *Benedicamus Domino* tropes from St George’s monastery, its character is conspicuously dissimilar: the text lines are of different length and connected only by the final assonance—*o*, the vowel of the exclamation *Domino*—instead of a regular rhyme; and the melody also consists of five phrases, formulated embellished descents from the upper *finalis d’* (of the D-Dorian mode) down through the full register, in a quick syllabic movement, in which it is impossible to detect any inner division or a regular occurrence of structurally important pitches. Instead, the trope concludes with a long melisma formulated as a descending sequence reminiscent of structured melismas known, for example, from earlier Aquitanian monophonic and polyphonic compositions.

In the chant repertory of St George’s monastery, this melisma constituted a familiar musical element. A similar concluding melisma is found at the end of the trope *Ad honorem sempiterni regis* (Table 1, no.21), which appears in the same St George’s manuscripts as *Laus Domino resonet*.⁴⁴ In *Ad honorem sempiterni regis*, however, this

melisma constitutes a final segment after a sequence of shorter syllabic phrases that move predominantly downwards in a matching melodic contour. Comparing both tropes, *Laus Domino resonet* appears to be a patchwork, a piece made up of two different parts, leading to the question of how the motet text and music reached St George’s convent, where it was performed as a monophonic chant and entirely stripped of any presumed serenity. According to the latest research, Czech lands (Bohemia and Moravia) likely came into contact with the Notre Dame repertory no later than in the mid 13th century, perhaps even earlier.⁴⁵ Possessing a manuscript with polyphonic repertory did not necessarily mean that its owners and all of the additional users of the next generation(s) had to understand its contents properly. The inscription of a motet voice would be perfectly comprehensible to anyone who tried to read it as a monophonic chant: the text and melody would remain faithfully preserved, only the rhythm, hidden from the uneducated user, would get lost, together of course with its polyphonic setting. Perhaps this partial comprehension is the scenario that is applicable here.⁴⁶

In conclusion, it is fruitful to reflect briefly on the complex question of how the *Benedicamus Domino*

trope repertory at St George's was incorporated into the convent's daily liturgical routine and complemented its spiritual life. The performance of tropes at St George's—as elsewhere—was reserved for the most important feasts of the church year, and especially for Christmastide. Processionals and other liturgical books usually also include a substantial group of untroped *Benedicamus Domino* chants, partly employing the same melodies as the troped items, which were probably intended for minor festivities.⁴⁷

Additional information is offered by the convent's mid-14th-century ordinal, CZ-Pu XIII E 14d. Descriptions of liturgical services are generally extremely precise in this manuscript and provide details not only about the selection of repertory and the organization of the ceremonies, but also about the personnel involved in their performance. For example, it is often specified who participated in the singing, whether it was all nuns (*cantrices, hebdomade*, both in the plural), *puelle* (girls) or also the priest, diaconus or canons.⁴⁸ Yet for the *Benedicamus Domino* tropes, the ordinal is remarkably unspecific, and the references to the use of *Benedicamus Exultemus et letemur* at the conclusion of Easter Vespers is exceptional. We can only deduce from formulations in some rubrics that they refer to the performance of a trope. Thus, for example, *Benedicamus de Nativitate Domini* is mentioned at the end of Lauds on Sunday within the Octave of the Nativity; similarly, *Post benedicamus de sancto Iohanne ewangelista* is included in the second Vespers of the feast of John the Evangelist.⁴⁹ A rubric in the Christmas Mass perhaps provides a cue to additional performance context, when stating: 'Ad summam missam Agnus sine trophis, quia ante missam cantantur' (During the Mass, the Agnus is performed without tropes, because these are sung before the Mass).⁵⁰ It is easy to imagine that communal singing before Mass on major feasts offered a space for the performance not only of Mass Ordinary tropes, but also of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes. Many trope texts suggest that they were meant to be performed jointly by the whole community (or its representatives), employing expressions, such as *nos* (we), *nostra concio* (our assembly), *hec concio* (this assembly) with active verbs of singing and dancing

such as *psallat, cantat, tripudiat* that are so characteristic of this genre.

Finally, a further use of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes is, quite surprisingly, documented in non-liturgical books, where it seems that the tropes were meant to be performed within private prayers, rather than being sung during liturgical services. *Amor patris et filii* (Table 1, no.20) is recorded in three manuscripts (A, B, C) as a chant for the feast of Pentecost; in two of them (A and B) it comes outside the series of *Benedicamus Domino* chants. In the context of the entire *Benedicamus Domino* trope repertory, *Amor patris et filii* is an extremely long piece, proceeding in mostly syllabic movement and using parallel *cursus*. It is sometimes designated as a *lai* or a sequence, and, while it appears as a monophonic chant at St George's, it is documented in a two-part version in British and Italian sources.⁵¹ Its text can best be described as a contemplation of the Holy Spirit, and in this function it was also incorporated into books that the Abbess Kunhuta and her nuns used for private prayer. In Kunhuta's so-called 'breviary' (the commonly used but imprecise designation of her *liber precum*), the text of *Amor patris* is included immediately following the complete set of texts from the Mass for Pentecost, *Dum sanctificatus fuero*, introducing a longer section with contemplative prayers to the Holy Spirit and the Virgin Mary.⁵² Such a recontextualization of liturgical sequences, hymns and tropes—for the *Benedicamus Domino* and for other genres—can be found in several more feasts in Kunhuta's prayer books, which indicates that new complementary chants were intended not only to be performed and (as we certainly can suppose) enjoyed during the liturgy, but also that at least some of them served additional educational and private devotional purposes.⁵³

APPENDIX

List of manuscript sources

- Prague, National Library of the Czech Republic (CZ-Pu)
 CZ-Pu VI G 3b (I)
 Processionale, St George's monastery, 1300–1325
 CZ-Pu VI G 5 (F)
 Processionale, St George's monastery, 1300–1350
 CZ-Pu VI G 10a (B)

Processionale, St George's monastery, 1280–1320
CZ-Pu VI G 10b (D)
Processionale, St George's monastery, 1280–1320
CZ-Pu VII G 16 (A)
Processionale, St George's monastery, 1300–1325
CZ-Pu VII G 17d
Breviarium Cunegundis, 1290–1320
CZ-Pu VII H 1 (E)
Corpus officiorum, St George's monastery, 1300–1350
CZ-Pu XII E 15a (C)
Processionale et hymnarius, St George's monastery,
1300–1335
CZ-Pu XIII H 3c (G)
Processionale, St George's monastery, 1300–1333

CZ-Pu XIII E 14b (K)
Psalterium, St George's monastery, 1150–1200
CZ-Pu XIII E 14d
Liber ordinarius, St George's monastery, 1347–1365
CZ-Pu XVI A 18 (H)
Psalterium, St George's monastery, mid-14th century
CZ-Pu XIV G 46
Corpus officiorum, St George's monastery, 1300–1350
Vyšší Brod, Klášterní knihovna (CZ-VB)
CZ-VB 42
Processionale, collection of liturgical chants and
cantiones, Vyšší Brod OCist, 1410

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¹ A short overview of individual liturgical traditions in Bohemia is included in H. Vlhová-Wörner, *Repertorium troporum Bohemiae medii aevi 1: Tropi Proprii Missae* (Prague, 2004), pp.32–5. Among recently published studies devoted

to individual music corpora and their late transmissions, are those addressing the Mass Ordinary (H. Vlhová-Wörner, 'Agnus pairing and disappearing: a contribution to the late chant tradition in Bohemia', in *ISM Study Group Cantus Planus 2014*, ed. J. Borders (Venice, 2020), pp.225–40) and the medieval motet (L. Hlávková, 'Using the past, shaping the present: tracing the tradition of specific polyphonic repertoires in Bohemian Utraquist sources (c.1450–1540)', in *Sounding the past: music as history and memory*, ed. K. Kügle (Turnhout, 2020), pp.199–213).

² Latin *cantiones* from Prague University circles are now edited in J. Ciglbauer et al., *Carmina clericorum: latinské duchovní písně 14. až 15. století ve středoevropském univerzitním a školském prostředí/ Sacred Latin songs from the 14th and 15th centuries in the Central European university and school milieu*, Monumenta liturgica Bohemica 4 (Chomutov, 2020). Hussite vernacular songs from the early 15th century are now available in a new edition, *Jistebnický kancionál*:

Praha, Knihovna Národního muzea, II c 7: kritická edice. 2. svazek: Cantionale/ The Jistebnice kancionál: Prague, National Museum Library II c 7: critical edition. 2, Cantionale, Monumenta liturgica Bohemica 3 (Chomutov, 2019).

³ G. M. Dreves, *Cantiones Bohemicae = Leiche, Lieder und Rufe des 13., 14. und 15. Jahrhunderts*, Analecta hymnica medii aevi 1 (Leipzig, 1886).

⁴ Notable, for example, is *Benedicamus regnanti cuncta* for St Wenceslas, the patron saint of Bohemia, included in the collection from the Cistercian monastery in Vyšší Brod from 1410 (CZ-VB 42, fol.176r).

⁵ *Benedicamus Domino* tropes from St George's monastery are available in modern synoptic transcriptions, see V. Plocek, *Zwei Studien zur ältesten geistlichen Musik in Böhmen*, 2 vols. (Giessen, 1985).

⁶ St George's church was consecrated as early as 925. By the end of the first millennium, it had become one of the oldest burial sites of the Přemyslid family and the centre of the cult of St Ludmila, the grandmother of St

Wenceslas and one of the patron saints of Bohemia. The monastery was abolished in 1782, but the relics of St Ludmila are still preserved in the church.

⁷ For a short overview of the history of St George's monastery, see *Umělecké památky Prahy*, ed. P. Vlček (Prague, 2000), pp.136–47.

⁸ J. Emler, *Libri confirmationum ad beneficia ecclesiastica Pragensem per archidiecesim*, iii–iv: *Ab anno 1373 usque ad annum 1390* (Prague, 1879), pp.193–4, and vi: *Ab anno 1399 usque ad annum 1410* (Prague, 1883), p.60. I thank Karel Pacovský (Charles University, Prague) for drawing my attention to these documents.

⁹ See, for example, the trope *Felix virgo, felix mater* to the offertory *Ave, Maria* that is documented from the St Vitus's Gradual of the 1360s and the St George's processional A from the beginning of the 14th century. See H. Vlhová-Wörner, *Repertorium troporum Bohemiae medii aevi 1*, OffTr 6. On the influence of the Hirsau reform, see J. Szendrei, 'Prager Quellen zum Hirsauer Choral', in *Cantus Planus 1996* (Budapest, 1998), pp.555–74.

¹⁰ The Dominican friar Kolda of Koldic, author of contemplative texts for the Abbess Kunhuta and her mentor, should be mentioned here in particular. On the Prague court and its intellectual milieu, see most recently K. Charvátová, *Mniši, dvořané, literáti: studie k cisterciáckému řádu a ke dvoru krále Václava II* (Prague, 2020).

¹¹ The only exception is the 12th-century psalter from Regensburg, later used at St George's (K), with copies of *Benedicamus Domino* tropes from as late as the 17th century.

¹² A full list of c.60 manuscripts from St George's monastery is currently under preparation by Renáta Modráková (The National Library of the Czech Republic).

¹³ Manuscripts from St George's monastery include some of the oldest notated inscriptions of *historiae* to the main patrons of Bohemia, St

Wenceslas (*Adest dies iubileus*) and St Ludmila (*Ecce iubar matutinum*).

¹⁴ See E. Urbánková and K. Stejskal, *Pasionál Přemyslovný Kunhuty/Passionale abbatissae Cunegundis* (Prague, 1975).

¹⁵ V. Plocek, *Catalogus codicum notis musicis instructorum qui in Bibliotheca publica rei publicae Bohemicae socialisticae—in Bibliotheca universitatis Pragensis servantur* (Prague, 1973), i, p.222.

¹⁶ Four *Benedicamus Domino* tropes are inserted at the bottom margins of fols.210v–211r and are followed by 14 untroped *Benedicamus Domino* chants for various feasts or seasons of the church year (fols.211v–213v). Melodies of untroped *Benedicamus Domino* chants are mostly derived from *Kyrie eleison* melodies that are found in late medieval Prague chant books.

¹⁷ Plocek, *Zwei Studien*, no.19. The chant appears as an addition from the 11th (?) century in a 9th-century collection of astronomical and mathematical treatises, München, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, Clm 560.

¹⁸ Plocek, *Zwei Studien*, no.2. The trope is documented in a number of sources from the 12th to the 14th centuries.

¹⁹ Plocek, *Zwei Studien*, no.11, with a list of c.20 concordances, mainly from Central Europe.

²⁰ Plocek, *Zwei Studien*, no.10. Inscriptions of the trope are found in Aquitanian sources (Paris, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, lat. 1139, and London, British Library, Add. Ms. 36881) and in the Las Huelgas Codex.

²¹ Plocek, *Zwei Studien*, no.34. The trope survived as a motet text and motetus melody in the Notre Dame manuscript *W₂* (see also below).

²² Plocek, *Zwei Studien*, no.38. Other sources come from Aquitaine (London, British Library, Add. Ms. 36881) and Spain (Codex Calixtinus, Santiago da Compostela, Biblioteca de la Catedral, s. s.).

²³ See H. Vlhová-Wörner, *Repertorium troporum Bohemiae*

medii aevi 2: Tropi Ordinarii Missae. Tropi ad Kyrie eleison et Gloria in excelsis Deo (Prague, 2006), pp.44–9, and H. Vlhová-Wörner, 'Mass Ordinary chants from Aquitaine in Prague: a complicated history', in *Paris, Bibl. Nat. f. l. 1139*, ed. O. Boudeau et al. (Turnhout, 2022), forthcoming, where it is proposed that the reception of French repertory (both north and south) is to be ascribed to the activity of Robert of Olomouc, a Cistercian monk of English origin. Robert studied in Paris and arrived in Prague at the end of the 12th century, occupying shortly thereafter the position of Bishop of Olomouc, a see he kept for four decades (1201–40).

²⁴ J. Černý, 'Středověký vícehlas v českých zemích [Medieval polyphony in Czech lands]', *Miscellanea musicologica*, xxvii–xxviii (1975), pp.20–3.

²⁵ This was proposed also in Černý, 'Středověký vícehlas', p.22.

²⁶ CZ-Pu xiv G 46, the part from the first half of the 14th century, fol.102r. Only the last stanza *Amen, amen* (etc.) appears in a two-part inscription; see also Černý, 'Středověký vícehlas', pp.26 and 86.

²⁷ See W. Arlt, *Ein Festoffizium des Mittelalters aus Beauvais in seiner liturgischen und musikalischen Bedeutung* (Cologne, 1973), Darstellungsband, p.179. In the 12th-century troper E-Mn 289, the trope consists of eight stanzas with three different texts for the refrain (fols.137v–138r).

²⁸ An edition of the *Visitatio sepulchri* play from St George's monastery was prepared by V. Plocek, *Melodie velikonočních slavností a her ze středověkých pramenů v Čechách* (Prague, 1989). See also a more recent critical edition by U. Evers and J. Janota, *Die Melodien zu den lateinischen Osterfeiern* (Berlin, 2013), I.ii, pp.1017–75 (LOO 799–805).

²⁹ In the troper from Seckau from 1345 (A-Gu 756), the trope *Surrexit Christus* follows the trope *Exultemus et letemur* (fols.188v–189v).

³⁰ In the version from E-Mn 289, the following stanza (not included in the version of St George's) quotes the second line of the *Alleluia Pascha nostrum*: 'Celebrantes hoc pascha sanctissimum/ epulemur veritatis azinum.'

³¹ See <http://cantusindex.org/search?t=dies+laetitiae&cid=&genre=All>.

³² See, for example, the version in E-Mn 289, where the lines proceed in a distinct syllabic movement with occasional use of two-note groups.

³³ CZ-Pu XIII E 14d, fols.82v–83r (roman here indicates red ink in the original).

³⁴ See, for example, CZ-Pu XIII E 14d, fol.76v: *In sacra nocte dictis quindecim psalmis graduum cantrix inponuit Domine labia mea* (etc.). *Sequitur invitatorium Alleluia, quatuor cantrices cantent Venite exultemus.*

³⁵ Plocek, *Zwei Studien*, p.92.

³⁶ The trope *Festivali melodia* is recorded in the manuscript D-Mbs 5130 from the 14th century; the trope *Iohannes flos ecclesiae* is known today only from St George's.

³⁷ On *Stimmtausch* melodies, see W. Arlt, 'Peripherie und Zentrum: vier Studien zu ein- und mehrstimmigen Musik des hohen Mittelalters, erste Folge', *Forum Musicologicum: Basler Studien zur Musikgeschichte*, i (1975), pp.169–222.

³⁸ E-Mn 289, fol.134r. Transcription in Arlt, *Ein Festoffizium*,

Darstellungsband, p.183, and in *Corpus monodicum digital* (<https://corpus-monodicum.de>; accessed 20 May 2022).

³⁹ Edition and commentary in H. Vlhová-Wörner, *Repertorium troporum Bohemiae Medii Aevi 3: Tropi ad Sanctus* (Prague, 2010), SaTr 12. All three trope elements to the three *Sanctus* invocations employ the same melody. The trope survived in a number of Prague manuscripts until the 16th century.

⁴⁰ The last summary of the complex situation is included in Vlhová-Wörner, 'Mass Ordinary Chants from Aquitaine in Prague and Central Europe.'

⁴¹ Apart from Mass Ordinary tropes, St Vitus's Cathedral included in its repertory a large number of troped lessons, some of them unknown in other sources.

⁴² D-W Cod. Guelf. 1099 Helmst., fols.126v–127r.

⁴³ G. A. Anderson, *The Latin compositions in fascicules VII and VIII of the Notre Dame manuscript Wolfenbüttel, Helmstadt 1099 (1206)* (New York, 1968), pp.32–3.

⁴⁴ Edition in Plocek, *Zwei Studien*, no.34.

⁴⁵ This question now appears in a new light, as a result of the discovery of fragments of two-part organa from the repertory of Notre Dame in a 15th-century manuscript from the milieu of Prague University. A study of the

Prague Notre Dame fragments and the reception of Ars Antiqua music in Bohemia in the 13th and 14th centuries is currently under preparation by Jan Ciglbauer and the author of the present article.

⁴⁶ Late medieval manuscripts from Bohemia transmit another version of this trope, documented for the first time in manuscripts from the Cistercian monastery of Vyšší Brod (CZ-VB 42, fol.F1). The trope is transformed here into a *cantio*: it refers to both upper voices of the motet, moves in the perfect rhythm of the third mode and is provided by a refrain employing new music text material and moving in the imperfect (trochaic) rhythm.

⁴⁷ *Benedicamus Domino* chants without tropes are included in manuscripts A, B, C, D, F, G and J. Detailed inventories of all manuscripts are included in Plocek, *Catalogus codicum*, p.274 *aliunde*.

⁴⁸ See, for example, the detailed description of liturgical services in the ordinal CZ-Pu XIII E 14d from the mid 14th century.

⁴⁹ CZ-Pu XIII E 14d, fol.22v and fol.25r.

⁵⁰ CZ-Pu XIII E 14d, fol.21r.

⁵¹ Plocek, *Zwei Studien*, no.42.

⁵² CZ-Pu VII G 17d, fols.92v–94r.

⁵³ On the incorporation of other liturgical chants (sequences, hymns) in the cycle of prayers in St George's monastery, see H. Vlhová-Wörner, 'Liturgical poetry and poetical liturgy', in *Motet cycles between devotion and liturgy*, ed. D. Filippi and A. Pavanello (Basel, 2019), pp.135–56.

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***Benedicamus Domino* tropes in the monastery of Benedictine nuns at St George's, Prague**

Within the rich spectrum of musical documents from medieval Bohemia, the corpus of tropes that survives in manuscripts from St George's convent at Prague Castle is perhaps the most important. Forty-two *Benedicamus Domino* tropes appear in manuscripts from the monastery—one of the richest and most important female foundations in Central Europe, with a small community of nuns from noble families—most of them compiled at the end of the 13th and the first decades of the 14th centuries. The collection includes *Benedicamus* tropes that were circulating in the wider Central European territory,

tropes that had their origins in the west and for which Prague constituted one of the furthest destinations within their dissemination, and a significant number of chants survive only in manuscripts from St George's and may have had their origins in this milieu. These *Benedicamus* tropes exhibit a striking variety of forms and richness in their melodic material: a number of polyphonic tropes employ a *Stimmtausch* technique, others are wholly structured as strophic songs with or without refrains. Many of the trope texts indicate that they were meant to be sung by both male and female communities at St George's, and their appearance in books with private prayers suggests that they may also have served an educational purpose.

Keywords: *Benedicamus Domino*; tropes; medieval nunneries; Ars Antiqua; Central Europe; *cantiones*